

Proposing Strategies For Translation Teachers To Avoid Cultural Hazards Faced By Iraqi Efl Students In Translation

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 08, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: October 12, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Translation, syntactic problems, semantic problems, cultural problems.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4081999</p>	<p><i>Translation is not merely an inter-linguistic process. It is more complex than replacing source language text with target language text and includes cultural and educational nuances that can shape the options and attitudes of recipients. Thus, there is a general agreement between translation scholars that translation is a powerful tool of communication of the meaning of a source language text by means of an equivalent target language text. The main problem of the current paper is that Iraqi EFL college students face difficulties in dealing with translation particularly at the early stages of learning. Particularly, they face a number of problems of different kinds including syntactic, semantic and cultural problems that require suitable solutions. This is due to the fact that English and Arabic are two different, having their own peculiarities. Thus, this paper aims to shed light on some problems Iraqi EFL face in translation and suggest some effective strategies for teachers of translation. The paper concludes that most difficulties they face are cultural followed by semantic and syntactic and finally lexical. Therefore, it suggests that the remedial solutions are attained with reference to types of text, context, readership, grammatical differences.</i></p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Syntax

According to Yule (1999:130), syntax is the set of rules, principles, and processes that govern the structure of sentences in a given language. Similarly, Crystal (2003: 145) states that syntax is the study of the rules governing the way words are combined to form sentences in a language.

1.2 Semantics

Semantics is the study of meaning of words, phrases, clauses and sentences in a language (Aitchison, 1997, 82). Semantics, as Thakur (2003:23) states, is the study of how meaning is and how it operates on word level and sentence level.

1.3 Culture

According to Newmark (1988:44), "culture is the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression", there are five major categories of culture:

- (1) Ecology: plants, animals, local winds, mountains, plains.
- (2) Materials: cultural food, clothes, housing, transport).
- (3) Social culture (work, and leisure).
- (4) Organizations, customs, ideas (political, social, legal, religious, artistic).
- (5) Gestures and habits (non-linguistic features).

1.4 Translation

According to Newmark (1981:133), translation is used to refer to all processes and methods used to transfer the meaning of the source language text into the target language. Further, Catford (1984: 210) maintains that translation consists of reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalence of the source language message.

Syntactic Problems2.

English and Arabic belong to two different language families, Germanic and Semitic. Thus, their syntax is totally different. Many syntactic features of English pose many problems of translation into Arabic because the two languages have different structural systems; therefore, students commit so many mistakes during translating. The main syntactic problems can be put forward as follows:

2.1 Translating the verb 'BE'

The main problem of translating the verb *be*, (i.e am, is, are, was, were, be, been) is to render literally into (يكون), which is a poor translation. Consider the following sentences:

- | | |
|--------------------|-----------------|
| 1- "I am a worker" | أنا أكون عاملاً |
| 2- "He is kind" | هو يكون طيباً |
| 3- "They are boys" | هم يكونون أولاد |

In these examples, Iraqi EFL students translate verb *be* literally, since these verbs should be omitted during translation. That is to say, changing the English verbal sentences into Arabic nominal ones: i.e. into a topic and comment (مبتدأ وخبر). The good translation should be like that:

- 1- "I am a worker" (أنا عامل)
- 2- "He is kind" (هو طيب)
- 3- "They are boys" (هم أولاد) (Ghazalla, 1993:33)

2.2 Translating the Verb "DO"

The main problem of translating verb '*do*' is that when it comes as an auxiliary, it poses many problems. The verb '*do*' is used in English as negative operator (forming negative). '*Do*' and '*does*' are used with the present simple, whereas '*did*' is used with the past. All these forms are meaningless in Arabic. Nevertheless, they have the function of indicating the tense of the verb (i.e. present or past). What is translated into Arabic is the negative particle "not" (لا) only: see the following examples:

- 4- "I do not like pigs" لا أحب الخنازير
- 5- "He does not write his homework" لا يكتب واجبه البيتي
- 6- "Some people do not smile" بعض الناس لا يبتسمون

The verb "*do*", as an interrogative operator) is also used to form the questions. And when translating it into Arabic, it always implies the question particle (هل) whether in the present or in the past. Consider the following sentences:

- 7- "Do you do your homework?" هل أديت واجبك البيتي
- 8- "Did Bill wait for you last night?" هل انتظرتك بيل ليلة البارحة

In addition, the verb "*do*" is used as emphatic device, and thus it should be taken into consideration while translating. Consider the following examples:

- 9- "Muslims do recite the Holy Koran everyday" يتلوا المسلمون القرآن كل يوم بالتأكيد
- 10- "The boys did behave well" أحسن الأولاد التصرف حقاً

(ibid: 34)

2.3 Translating the Verb "HAVE"

The verb '*have*' is used as an auxiliary to perform important grammatical functions. In this case, it is meaningless in Arabic, and the students can ignore it altogether: Consider the following examples:

- 11- "The students have left early". غادر العمال باكراً
 - 12- "The patient has had the medicine". تناول المريض الدواء
 - 13- "He has just had the ticket". حصل على التذكرة لتوه
- (IbuRisha, 1987: 134)

And when it is used as a main verb, a lot of EFL students translate the verb '*have*' into one version only, that is: (يملك). See the following example:

- 14- "She has money". هي تملك نقوداً/ عندها نقود/ في حوزتها نقود/ لديها نقود/ معها نقود

(ibid: 135)

2.4 Translating Modals

There are ten modal verbs in English. They are '*can/ could, may/might, will/ would, shall/ should, must, ought to*'. They pose few problems in translation (Aziz, 1982: 210)

These modals are not verbs in Arabic when they are used to refer to future either in the present (will, shall) or in the past (would) they mean the future particle (س/ سوف). Thus, they are translated into (سوف) or (س) regardless of the possibility of the reference of the latter to the near future, and the former to the far future.

- 15- "They will help us". سوف يساعدوننا/ سيساعدوننا

Other modal verbs such as '*can, may, and must*' are usually understood by the students to mean one word each (يستطيع, يمكن, يجب). But the case is not always so. Sometimes, they imply two words. The problem becomes clearer when the students translate them from English into Arabic.

- 16- "We can walk". نستطيع أن نمشي

We cannot say:

- 17- "We must walk". يجب علينا أن نمشي

In certain cases, '*shall*', particularly in legal language, has a special use. It is not used to refer to future, but to obligation.

- 19- "The defendant shall appear before court now".

يجب على المدعي عليه أن يمثل أمام المحكمة الآن

3. Semantic Problems

The main problems posed to EFL Iraqi students of translation are semantic problems. The central semantic problem faced by students is their literal translation of almost all words. That is, they dedicate themselves to

translate all words, phrases and expressions directly and they must find the equivalent in Arabic. The main semantic problems can be summarized as follows:

3.1 Translating Synonymy

In most cases, the main problem the students face is that they understand all synonymous words as absolute synonyms only (Aitchison, 1997: 220). Consider the following examples:

- 20- "He is very angry" هو غاضب جداً
 21- "He is very agitated" هو ساخط جداً
 22- "He is very impatient" هو نافذ الصبر جداً

When the students find the equivalent word in Arabic for, say, agitated (ساخط), they give the most suitable version. They can use the general translation (غاضب جداً).

- 23- "The soldiers stood to their arms in the battle".
 can be translated into following versions in Arabic.

- 1 - ثبت الجنود في الميدان.
 2 - صمد الجنود في المعركة.
 3 - استتبسل الجنود في ساحة المعركة.

3.2 Translating Collocations

Collocation is the "habitual co-occurrences of individual lexical items" (Crystal, 1981: 212). The main problem for students is to find the proper Arabic equivalent collocation.

- 24- "Addled eggs" بيض فاسد
 25- "Bad milk" حليب فاسد
 26- "Putrid fish" سمك فاسد
 27- "Rotten fruit" فاكهة فاسدة

At first, these collocations pose some problems to the students while translating them into Arabic, because it is not easy to find Arabic equivalents for the English ones. The solution is simply to use the adjective (فاسد) with all kinds of bad food .

3.3 Translating Idioms

An idiom is a fixed phrase whose form is usually unchangeable, and whose meaning is always the same. Consider the following examples:

- 28- "Passing the exam is not a bed of roses."
 النجاح في الامتحان ليس طريقاً مفروشاً بالورد

The above example is translated directly, but it should be understood indirectly. Thus, the intended meaning can be as follows.

- 29- "Passing the exam is difficult".
 النجاح في الامتحان امر صعب

The main problem for the students to translate idioms is that idioms are entirely indirect and cannot be understood from the direct meaning of the words. Consider the following example.

- 30- "My car is second hand" سيارتي مستعملة
 31- "She is a dog in the manager." أنها لا ترحم ولا تدع الرحمة تنزل
 (Seidi, 1988: 135)

3.4 Translating Polysemies

Polysemy occurs when a word has more than one meaning. The main problem is that some polysemic words different meanings (Yule, 1995: 122). Consider the following examples.

- 32- "The boy broke the window". كسر الولد النافذة
 33- "The athlete broke the world record". حطم العداء الرقم العالمي
 34 "Let us break bread together". لناكل خبزاً وملحاً معاً

To overcome the difficulty of translating polysemic words, the students should take into account the context in which these words are used.

4. Cultural Problems

It is a known fact that communication between cultures can be achieved through translation. Newmark (1981: 183) argues that there is a cultural value in translation. Language is partly the reflection of a culture-translators like linguists tend to define culture as the sum of people's customs and ways of thinking. According to Newmark (ibid: 184), there are five categories of culture including ecology, material culture, social culture organizations, customs, ideas and habits. Thus, knowledge of the target culture is crucial for successful English-Arabic translation.

4.1 Cultural Equivalent

The idea of cultural equivalent is to look for the expression in Arabic, which is used exactly in the same context, to give a meaning that is perfectly identical to that of the source language expression. Consider the following examples.

- 35- "The British Council" المركز الثقافي البريطاني
 36- "A fox is not taken twice in the same snare. لا يلدغ المؤمن من جحر مرتين.
 The cultural equivalent is used as a functional equivalent – that is, the British Council performs the identical functions of (المركز الثقافي البريطاني). The same applies to the fox and the Islamic term (المؤمن) (the true believer) (ibid: 185) .

4.2 Accepted Standard Translation

Some English cultural terms have become established in Arabic, especially in technology (C. F. car industry, computer, internet). See the following examples:

- 37- "Software & hardware". برامج الحاسوب ومعدات الحاسوب
 38- "Spare parts" قطع غيار سيارات
 (Aziz, 1982: 93)

4.3 Deculturalization

This procedure is kind of deculturalization of a cultural terms, so that it becomes normalized and neutralized in target language. Consider the following examples:

- 39- "Cremlin" القصر الرئاسي الروسي
 40- "Westminister" مبنى البرلمان البريطاني

These terms are translated into an ordinary Arabic language to avoid ambiguity of a direct literal translation of words since they are culture specific terms. (ibid: 94).

4.4 Paraphrase

Paraphrase is a kind of short explanation. "It is used when there is no other way to illustrate the unclear cultural term in translation (Newmark, 1981:220). Consider the following examples:

- 41- Ham شرائح لحم الخنزير
 42- Shavian أسلوب الكاتب برنارد شو الساحر
 43- Selva غابة الأمطار الاستوائية

The terms cannot be translated into Arabic by one equivalent word only, because they will be confusing, rather, they need to be paraphrased (ibid: 221).

5. General Results

Having scored the test sheets , it has been found that the total errors committed by the subjects to their translations of the prescribed text are (317).The most errors committed are cultural ,with 113errors forming (35.64%) ,therefore occupying the first rank among other types of errors. The grammatical errors come in the second rank (after the cultural errors) recording (99) errors constituting (31.23%). Sixty six cases of lexical errors have been computed, having a rate of (20.82%). The final rank has been occupied by the *spelling* errors, in that only 39 cases of such errors have been calculated with the percentage of (12.30%).The following are the detailed account of each type of errors made by the students .

5.1 Cultural Errors

Focusing on the cultural errors, students seem to show weakness in translating the cultural items from their native language into the target ones. Obviously, and as the examples revealed ,most students resort to their Arabic culture to transfer the meaning of the target language ,e.g. showing cultural interference as supported in the following examples :

-The Arabic sentence :

ويزور الضريح...ولا سيما في زيارتي عاشوراء وذكرى الأربعين...

has been translated differently by some subjects with various wrongly cultural counterparts :

I-.....in the two visits of Ashora and Alarbaeen memories .

II-.....in the two visiting Ashoora and 40 memory .

III-.....to the visitations twice and memorization 40 .

Another example of cultural failure is noticed :

للضريح منائر جميلة جدا وعالية جدا ...

I-for the tomb has beautiful minarites very high .

II-the shrain sweet and high towers .

III-The minerates are in shrine and very high .

The expressions ضريح and منائر جميلة have inappropriately translated into tombs/shrain, minareets/towers and sweet respectively .

Again, some students failed to give suitable equivelant translation for the phrase

(Peace Be Upon Him) عليه السلام(ع),they use the Arabic everyday salutation: instead ,in the following sentence :

ويقع ضريح الأمام العباس (ع) في مركز...

Being affected by the Arabic conventional use of language , some subjects use "Salam on him " or "Salam on you " as in :

I-The Imam Abas(*Salam on you*) tomb is in the center

II-Abass(*Salam on him*)shrain located in the center...

5. 2 Grammatical Errors

Grammatical errors are marked by incorrect use of syntactic and morphological constructions:

A. Tense

Students freely jump from one tense to another without paying attention to the situation involved , they employ **Past Simple** to indicate **Present** events or states ,or **Present Continuous / Present Perfect** to refer to constant/habitual actions or events .

ويقع ضريح الأمام الحسين...

I-The shrine of Imam Hussein lied

ويزور الضريح عدد كبير جدا...

II-People People are visiting the tomb...

III-People have visited the shrine ...

Moreover, the subjects misuse the 3rd person singulars and use instead either bare infinitive or be + V...:

IV-Many people **come** the shrine

V- The shrine **is lie**

B. Passive Voice

A second syntactic error committed by some students is the misuse of passive voice ; they often neglect the exploitation of the verb **be** in the passive construction(**be + Vpp**) :

يقع ضريح الأمام العباس ...

Imam Abbass Tomb **located** in...

ويزور الضريح عدد كبير جدا ايضا...

-The tomb is visited by many people .

C. Definite Article :

It seems that most subjects misuse the article “**the**“ in the suitable slot ,they either manipulate the indefinite article “**a**” or they leave it bare :

ولا سيما زيارتي عاشوراء وذكرى الأربعين ...

I-Not that in the two visits of Ashoora and ...arbaeenmemory .

II-particularly in visitation twice of Ashoraand 40 memorization .

وللضريح منائر جميلة جدا ...

III-To ...shrine are beautiful minareets .

IV-...shrine surrounded by big minarits .

5.3. Lexical Errors

Some subjects are found to inappropriately utilize certain lexical items which result in a semantically broken sentences .For example, they use the words **lay,sweet** and **memory**to refer to the words **lie** , **pretty** and **anniversary** respectively and **tomb and area** to refer to the word **shrine** .

6. Suggested Strategies to Overcome Cultural Hazards

Regarding the above results as well as the literature review, the researchers of the current paper have proposed specific strategies in an attempt to overcome the cultural barriers that EFL Iraqi students usually encounter in translation as follows:

6.1 Transliteration

The term second language is taken to the target language text :

e.g. :=كويت **Kuwait** =كويت **Jassim** جاسم := .

6.2 Domestication

The word of the 'second language is conveyed into target language and the inscription is ascribed to the writing system of the target language:

e.g. :=قهوة **Coffee** =حشاش **Assassin** .

6.3 Cultural Equivalence

The word of the second language is substituted by a cultural word of target language:

e.g. :=جو **Atmosphere** =عاصفه **Storm** .

6.4 Synonymy

The word of the second language is rendered into a neutral word of the target language:

e.g. :=رباب **Cloud** =غيث **Rain** .

6.5 Descriptive Equivalence

The description and or function of a view or an idea embodied in the second language can be explained by the translator. This process commonly causes long wording :

e.g. := سمل **to gouge out** =عينه **Non other one** .

6.6 Familiar Translation

The word of the second language is substituted by a formerly recognized translation of the word in the second language in the target language.

e.g. := **Averroes** ابن رشد = **Avicena** ابن سينا .

6.7 Componential Analysis

The word of the second language is substituted by a more common word of the target language with additional one or sometimes more componential sense to arrive at the meaning which is not found in the first word of the target language. It seems that it is like having descriptive equivalence, however shorter and does not encompass the purpose of the idea of the word in the second language.

e.g. := **Hunting dog : Saluki** سلوقي = **Winter fruit** رمان .

6.8 Reduction

A word or phrase as a translation entity in the second language can substituted by a word or phrase in the target language which does not include a portion of the word meaning in the second language:

e.g. := **Caliph** خليفة رسول الله = **Synecdoche** بدل البعض من الكل وبدل الكل من البعض (مجاز مرسل)

6.9 Expansion

A word or phrase ,as a translation element in the second language can be substituted by a word or phrase in the target language which embraces word sense plus something else in the second language:

e.g. := **Chapter** = سورة من القرآن الكريم = **Toe of the hoof** سننك

6.10 Additional Note

An additional note is usually given after the translation of a word or phrase in the target language This additional element is obviously not a part of the translation:

a. e.g. := **Al-Karada** الكرادة “ **with a foot note reads : One of Baghdad suburbs [neighborhood] .**

b. = **Qais** فيس” **with a foot note reads : Qais is the hero of a famous pop love story .**

6.11 Deletion

A word or phrase in the second language , being considered as a translation element, is omitted in the target language:

e.g. : **Muslut A. (2012)**

O! Long time, you are pardoned. Be kind تنسي أباها أنها أبنه سبعة فأذا بها من أمتع الخلان
...To a back burdened with guilt and drink .

6.12 Modulation

As a translation entity, a word or phrase in the second language can be rendered into a word or phrase in the target language; yet this process comprises a change in the viewpoint:

e.g. := **I bought from him** اباعني = **received a letter from him** .
 ارسل لي رساله

Often translators (in translating the above phrases) conceive the word or the phrase as predicting somehow different viewpoints or generally a category of thought .

7. Conclusions

The current paper has come up with the following conclusions:

- 1- Problems of translation are posed by the grammar, words, style, and culture of the source language when translated into the target language.
- 2- The syntactic problems stem from the fact that EFL students use literal translation which is a poor translation.
- 3- EFL students use free translation when they translate grammatical structure from English to Arabic.
- 4- The semantic problems stem from the fact that some lexical items of SL cannot be replaced by an equivalent of TL.
- 5- Cultural problems arise from the difference of culture of the two languages together with the lack of cultural correspondence.
- 6- The main solutions for these problems are suggested on the bases of the types of text, context, readership, grammatical differences, etc.
- 7- Being aware of the cultural differences will have a bearing in the cultural concepts in one language and the way they are expressed in another language.
- 8- The speakers of each language portray the world around in a specific way in accordance with their properties and the way this expressed in their language .This goes along with their perception of culture-specific concepts .

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